

Deliverable 6.2

FoSSNet Website

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FoSSNet Website

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents a short overview of the project website, launched in its first version by M5. The website represents the platform containing all information and references about the project, including news, deliverables, opportunities for stakeholders and more. It is developed following the strategy contained in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D6.1), to be delivered by M6 but already available in an internal and mature version.

The website launched at this stage represents a first version containing the essential information for ensuring the project's visibility and the engagement with the relevant actors. The website will be extended through the creation of new pages, additional functionalities as soon as FoSSNet will start activities and produces results in other WPs. Moreover, the project will be constantly updated with resources, events and news.

Further changes to the website structure will be described in the upcoming versions of D6.1.

Document information

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SFSN	Sustainable Food Systems Network
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The document presents the structure of the project website, launched in its first version on the 28th June 2024. Additional information, including KPIs to evaluate its success and plan changes, will be provided in D6.1.

2 FoSSNet website

The website is the entry point and the primary information source of the FoSSNet project, informing about its scopes, activities, partners, news, events and results, and it will be connected to the project's channels and media (i.e. FoSSNet LinkedIn page, SciFoodHealth social media accounts, and SFSN).

EUFIC coordinated the website creation process, taking care of the WP leaders' needs and requirements, and was responsible for the technicalities, including the selection of a supplier for the website technical development, and content creation in collaboration with project partners.

As a first step, EUFIC, bought the domain <https://www.fossnet.eu/> and defined the first structure for the website. Three potential suppliers were asked for quotations and provided their best offers. After the evaluation of offers, at the end of March 2024, EUFIC selected BoostU as the supplier for the FoSSNet website.

According to the contract, the website is being developed using WordPress as Content Management Systems (CMS), preferred to the customised ones because of its open-source nature. The FoSSNet website is hosted on the EUFIC servers, that are based in the EU (France). According to the contract signed with BoostU, the website will be maintained alive for three years after the end of the project (till January 2031): during this period, the company will update the installed plug-ins, monitor the security and maintain the Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate, thus allowing users to browse the website without any issues.

EUFIC prepared the design and framework for the website structure after consulting various project partners. The content of each page and section was produced by EUFIC with the contribution of FoSSNet partners, and additional feedback was asked once the design and structure of the website were finalised. EUFIC was responsible for the latest fine-tuning of the texts provided and for their uploading on the website. The FoSSNet website (Deliverable 6.2) was launched in Month 5 (June 2024).

The website will be updated on a regular basis with the project's updates, lay articles, details about the FoSSNet conferences and relevant events, public deliverables, scientific publications, and other communication materials. The website structure and featured sections are described below.

2.1 Homepage

It represents the entry point of the website, containing simple and attractive messages for the identified target audiences to engage them in the project activities. Designed to guarantee users' accessibility and in line with the visibility standards, it will:

- connect the users to the other website resources, tools and sections;
- show in brief the project description (linking to a more detailed page) and the three main pillars of the project;
- show in brief the conferences organised by the project;
- show in brief the latest news and next events;
- re-address the users to other project's channels (FoSSNet LinkedIn, and SciFoodHealth X);
- give the possibility to subscribe for receiving news and information on FoSSNet results and activities (newsletter created by EUFIC and operated via Brevo tool);
- give the possibility to contact using the FoSSNet generic email;
- inform the user about the cookies policy (giving it the possibility to choose the options in compliance with the current legislation) and know more about the privacy policy (prepared by RUC and EUFIC);
- acknowledge the project funding.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the FoSSNet website – Homepage

2.2 About

This section will provide the main information on the project, showing:

- fundamental information about FoSSNet (project overview, goals and approach);
- members of the consortium, with a logo and brief description of each partner (including their role in the project);
- (when settled) the FoSSNet Advisory board and its members, including each one's picture, the logo of the entity they represent and a short biography.

Figure 2: Screenshots of the FoSSNet website – About page

2.3 Network

This section will provide functional information related to the network including:

- description of the network;
- information on how to join the network;
- explanation on the benefits of joining;
- an interactive map to present entities that will be developed at a later stage, after the website launch.

Currently, this page provides general information about the network.

2.4 News and events

In this section, all the news and upcoming events interesting for all the defined target audiences are shown in detail, including information on both the past and upcoming events. This page is connected to the preview available on the FoSSNet homepage.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the FoSSNet website – News page

Figure 4: Screenshot of the FoSSNet website – Events page

2.5 Conferences

This section will provide detailed information on upcoming conferences organised by the consortium, including the presentation of each conference, related news and resources. The Conferences page is also connected to the preview available on the FoSSNet website.

2.6 Getting involved

This section will include practical information on main activities in which external stakeholders can be involved and where they can find relevant information about the key activities implemented by FoSSNet, such as:

- results of the analysis of the food systems education systems;
- Summer schools;
- results of the FoSSNet research activities (i.e., on the true cost of food);
- output/outcomes/results, and reports from the project;
- any other resources and all materials produced by the project.

Since it is based on activities that will be implemented during a later stage of the project, this section is available only in a basic version and it will be constantly integrated.

2.7 Contact us

This page will show users how to get in touch with the FoSSNet project, namely a contact form (responses sent to the email info@fossnet.eu).

Figure 5: Screenshot of the FoSSNet website – Contact page

3 Conclusion and next steps

The FoSSNet website was launched online on the 27th of June, in a version that is able to provide the most important information about the project but that still needs to be enriched with additional contacts, due to the fact that the project is in its initial stages and some activities have not started or not produced results yet. However, the technical structure is ready and prepared also for such content (for instance, the interactive map to show the FoSSNet network is already set, and it will be launched as soon as the relevant information for it is available).

The official promotion of the website with social media posts and promotion is planned for the 1st of July.

During the next months, EUFIC, supported by partners, will enrich the website with new content and it will take care of its technical maintenance.